

Primary Angioplasty Versus Stenting for Endovascular Management of Intracranial Atherosclerotic Disease Following Acute Ischemic Stroke

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Abstract

Background—The future of neuroendovascular treatment for intracranial atherosclerotic disease (ICAD) has been debated since the results of SAMMPRIS reflected poor outcomes following endovascular therapy. There is currently a large spectrum of current management strategies. We compared historical outcomes of patients with ICAD and stroke that were treated with angioplasty-alone versus stent placement.

Methods—We extracted a population from the Nationwide Inpatient Sample (NIS) (2005–2011) and the National Inpatient Sample (NIS) (2012) composed of patients with ICAD and infarction that were admitted nonelectively and received endovascular revascularization. Patients treated with thrombectomy or thrombolysis were excluded. Categorical variables were compared with Chi-squared tests. Binary logistic regression was performed to evaluate mortality while controlling for age, sex, severity, and comorbidities.

Results—About 2059 admissions met our criteria. A majority were treated via stent placement (71%). Angioplasty-alone had significantly higher mortality (17.6% vs. 8.4%, $P<0.001$), but no difference in iatrogenic stroke rate (3.4% vs. 3.6%, $P=0.826$), compared to stent placement. The adjusted odds ratio of mortality for stented patients was 0.536 (95% CI: 0.381–0.753, $P<0.001$) in comparison to patients treated with angioplasty alone.

Conclusions—This study found the risk of mortality to be elevated following angioplasty alone in comparison to revascularization with stent placement, without a corresponding significant difference in iatrogenic stroke rate. This may represent selection bias due to patient characteristics not defined in the database, but it also may indicate that patients with ICAD and acute stroke have increased odds of stenosis that is refractory to angioplasty alone and have a high risk of mortality without revascularization.

Keywords

Acute ischemic stroke; angioplasty; endovascular; intracranial stenosis; stent

INTRODUCTION

Intracranial atherosclerotic disease (ICAD) is one of the most common causes of stroke worldwide [1]. Historical treatment has been confined to medical management, but recent advances in endovascular technology have facilitated cerebral reperfusion via percutaneous transluminal angioplasty and stent placement. Following the food and drug administration (FDA) approval of the Wingspan Stent System (Stryker Inc., MI, USA) in 2005, there was optimism for the advancement of endovascular therapy for ICAD [2]. A prospective clinical trial, stenting and aggressive medical management for prevention of recurrent stroke in intracranial stenosis (SAMMPRIS), was launched to evaluate its safety and efficacy. This study was halted early due to an elevated

30-day stroke and death rate in the endovascular therapy group [3].

The future of neuroendovascular treatment of ICAD has since been debated. A recent survey of interventionalists at the International Stroke Conference revealed a large spectrum of current clinical management strategies [4]. A majority of participants (85%) were willing to randomize patients with symptomatic ICAD in future trials, with 29% indicating that the next trial should be angioplasty-alone compared with aggressive medical therapy [4].

To examine this future direction, we compared the historical outcomes of patients with symptomatic ICAD

and stroke that were treated with angioplasty-alone versus those treated with stent placement. Our null hypothesis was that patients in both groups would have similar clinical disposition at discharge.

METHODS

We analyzed discharge data from the National Inpatient Sample and Nationwide Inpatient Sample (NIS), Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project (HCUP), Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (Rockville, MD) from 2005 to 2012. This database represents approximately a 20% stratified sample of U.S. nonfederal hospitals. Detailed information on the design of the NIS is available at <http://www.hcup-us.ahrq.gov>. The NIS is a de-identified database and did not require IRB review in accordance with the Code of Federal Regulations, 45 CFR 46.

Patients were identified in the NIS using a combination of International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM) diagnosis and procedure codes. Only patients with a nonelective admission were included, as to eliminate nonsymptomatic cases whose condition permitted adequate time to schedule intervention. We required a primary diagnosis of intracranial stenosis/occlusion with infarction (434.01, 434.11, or 434.91) along with intracranial stent placement (00.65) or intracranial angioplasty alone (00.62). Patients receiving mechanical thrombectomy (ICD-9-CM 39.74) or rtPA (ICD-9-CM 99.10) were excluded to improve homogeneity of the cohorts and to minimize the impact of patients with a combined diagnosis of stenosis and thromboembolic occlusions.

Case severity was determined using the all patient refined-diagnosis-related group (APR-DRG) risk of mortality. This proprietary four-point ordinal scale (minor, moderate, major, extreme risk of mortality) developed by 3M Health Information Systems has been validated to predict mortality more reliably than other severity measures using administrative data sets and has been used as a severity indicator in prior stroke studies [5–8]. Any cases classified as minor were excluded from analysis ($n=6$). Individual comorbidity burden was determined using a modified Charlson comorbidity index (CCI) based on ICD-9-CM codes [9]. This index is a weighted-patient score designed to account for various comorbidities, including history of cancer, as well as cardiac, vascular, pulmonary, neurologic, endocrine, renal, hepatic, gastrointestinal, and immune disorders. Elixhauser measures, as provided in the NIS disease severity file, were used in place of similar Charlson

measures and weighted accordingly, with the exception that mild liver disease was assigned three points [10]. Previous studies have demonstrated that slight modifications to the CCI have minimal impact on the overall score [11,12].

The primary economic measures were hospital cost and length of stay. Hospital charges were converted to costs using the group-weighted average cost-to-charge ratio (GAPICC) for years 2005 to 2011, and the cost-to-charge ratio (CCR) for 2012. The costs were adjusted to 2014 levels using the inflation calculator provided by the Bureau of Labor Statistics (http://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm) [13]. The primary clinical outcome was in-patient death, and the secondary clinical outcomes were iatrogenic stroke (997.02, postoperative cerebrovascular infarction or hemorrhage) and iatrogenic cardiac complication (997.1, cardiac arrest or insufficiency, cardiorespiratory failure, or heart failure during or resulting from the procedure). These iatrogenic complication codes have been utilized in prior studies on patients treated with stent placement [14–17].

Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 17 (IBM Corporation, Armonk NY, USA). To obtain national estimates, discharge weights were applied. Categorical variables were compared with Chi-squared tests and continuous variables were compared with Mann–Whitney U-tests. Generalized linear models with a gamma distribution and log link function were used to analyze the length of hospital stay and the total inflation-adjusted hospital cost. The analysis considered age, CCI, gender, APR-DRG risk of mortality, and revascularization procedure (stent vs. angioplasty alone). Continuous variables were transformed into categorical variables; CCI by quartiles and age by the categories defined in an analysis of the North American Symptomatic Carotid Endarterectomy Trial (NASCET)—<65 years, 65–74 years, and >74 years [18]. The exponential parameter estimates were reported as the effect ratio for each variable, along with their 95% confidence interval (CI). The primary clinical outcome was assessed in binary logistic regression using the enter method and controlled for the same variables as previously listed. Odds ratios and their 95% CI were reported. A probability value of 0.01 was considered statistically significant in order to nominally control for type-I error.

RESULTS

About 2059 nonelective admissions were identified with a primary diagnosis of intracranial stenosis/occlusion with infarction that were treated with endovascular

Table 1. Characteristics and outcomes of patients admitted with a primary diagnosis of intracranial stenosis/occlusion with infarction.

	Stent (N=1463)	Angioplasty Alone (N=596)	P
Age	65 (55–75)	67 (57–77)	<0.001
Male	854 (58.4)	328 (55.1)	0.177
Hypertension	1219 (83.3)	426 (71.5)	<0.001
Charlson comorbidity index			
0	459 (31.4)	217 (36.5)	
1	518 (35.4)	239 (40.2)	
2	263 (18.0)	54 (9.1)	<0.001
>2	223 (15.2)	85 (14.3)	
APR-DRG risk of mortality			
Moderate	915 (62.5)	293 (49.2)	
Major	287 (19.6)	148 (24.9)	<0.001
Extreme	261 (17.8)	154 (25.9)	
Location/teaching status of hospital			
Rural	NR	NR	
Urban, nonteaching	155 (10.6)	67 (11.3)	<0.001
Urban, teaching	1309 (89.4)	518 (87.1)	
Weekend admission	329 (22.5)	157 (26.3)	0.061
Length of stay, d	7 (5–12)	9 (5–14)	<0.001
Cost, \$	40,485 (29,671–58,937)	39,641 (26,599–65,992)	0.533
Iatrogenic stroke	52 (3.6)	20 (3.4)	0.826
Iatrogenic cardiac complication	24 (1.6)	NR	0.162
Mortality	123 (8.4)	105 (17.6)	<0.001
Discharge home	525 (35.9)	148 (24.9)	<0.001

Comparisons are performed between endovascular approaches for revascularization.

Continuous variables presented as median (1st quartile–3rd quartile). Categorical variables presented as *n* (%). NR: not reportable as cell size ≤10.

Table 2. The odds of mortality following endovascular revascularization.

Population	Reference category	Odds ratio	95% CI	P
Stent	Angioplasty	0.536	0.381–0.753	<0.001
Female	Male	0.791	0.571–1.097	0.160
Age				
< 65	>74	1.215	0.821–1.798	0.331
65–74	>74	0.912	0.591–1.407	0.676
APR-DRG risk of mortality				
Major	Extreme	0.012	0.006–0.023	<0.001
Moderate	Extreme	0.226	0.158–0.323	<0.001
Charlson comorbidity index				
0	>2	1.811	1.129–2.906	0.014
1	>2	1.927	1.205–3.081	0.006
2	>2	1.551	0.879–2.737	0.130

revascularization. This represents <0.1% of all cases of ICAD and stroke that were admitted to US hospitals from 2005–2012 (2059/2,909,745). About 1511 involved revascularization via intracranial stent placement and 622 were intracranial angioplasty alone (Table 1). The median patient age was 66 years (IQR: 20) and there was a greater proportion of male patients (57.4%).

The mortality rate following stent placement was less than half of that observed following treatment with angioplasty alone (8.4% vs. 17.6%, $P<0.001$). There was no significant difference in iatrogenic stroke rate or iatrogenic cardiac complications between treatment groups (Table 1).

Mortality was additionally investigated in binary logistic regression in order to adjust for confounding variables in the dataset. Patients with low comorbidity burden were more likely to die than their more disease stricken counterpart (Table 2). As expected, (APR-DRG) risk of mortality had the greatest association with in-hospital mor-

tality, with patients classified in the most serious category (extreme) experiencing the greatest odds of mortality. The odds of mortality following stent placement was significantly reduced in comparison to treatment with angioplasty alone (Table 2).

The factor having the biggest impact on cost and length-of-stay was the APR-DRG risk of mortality (Fig. 1). In multivariate analysis, the difference in length-of-stay and cost between treatment groups was insignificant at the $P<0.01$ level (Fig. 1).

DISCUSSION

This study examined patients with ICAD and stroke that were treated acutely with endovascular revascularization. Comparisons were performed between approaches, stent placement or angioplasty alone, and multivariate analysis was used to further examine mortality and economic measures while adjusting for confounding variables.

Figure 1. Multivariate analysis of economic measures. Length of stay and hospital costs are presented as the effect ratio along with the 95% confidence interval. Points to the right of 1.0 reflect an increase in the effect ratio relative to the indicated reference category. Points to the left of 1.0 reflect a decrease in the effect ratio relative to the indicated reference category. * indicates significance at the $P < 0.01$ level. CCI: modified Charlson comorbidity index, ROM: all patient refined-diagnosis-related group risk of mortality, Ref: Reference

The number of studies involving this specific population and nonelective endovascular intervention are limited. A study by Gupta et al. involved 18 patients who failed medical therapy and were thought to be at high risk of imminent stroke [19]. The authors treated them with urgent endovascular revascularization via angioplasty and demonstrated that the technique was feasible but that the mortality rate in neurologically unstable patients was high (3/18, 17%). This number compares well with the documented mortality rate of 17.6% for the angioplasty-alone group in the current study.

The in-hospital mortality rate in the group treated with stent placement in the present study was 8.4%. This is comparable to the results by Fiorella et al. that document a mortality rate of 6% (3/48) in patients with a history of stroke and treated with the Wingspan stent [20]. A retrospective study by Guo et al. included 11 patients with intracranial MCA occlusions that were treated with emergent stent placement without thrombolysis and documented a similar mortality rate of 9% (1/11) [21]. Our mortality rate following stent placement was higher than in the stent-treated group from SAMMPRIS at the 30-day mark (2.2%) or The Wingspan Study (2.3%) [3,22]. However, it should be noted that the SAMMP-

RIS trial included patients with transient ischemic attack and excluded patients with neurological signs within 24 h of enrollment [3]. A similar criterion was in The Wingspan Study and required patients to be at least seven days after stroke [22]. While the presenting symptoms of the patients in the current study are not known, they were admitted nonelectively and diagnosed with stroke. This likely speaks to the inclusion of neurologically unstable patients with expected worse outcomes than those enrolled in clinical trials.

The increased mortality following angioplasty alone in comparison to stent placement was presumably not driven by a surge in iatrogenic cardiac complications. The low cardiac complication rate in both arms (1.4%) was comparable to the 30-day rate in the endovascular arm of the SAMMPRIS trial (2.2%) [3]. There was also not a difference in the rate of iatrogenic stroke between groups indicating that thromboembolic or hemorrhagic complications may not account for the difference in mortality. The observed stroke rate in the present study (3.5%) was lower than the 30-day rate in the endovascular arm of SAMMPRIS (14.7%) [3]. This is likely attributable to two areas. First, we could not include any strokes that occurred between discharge and the typical

30-day evaluation in clinical trials, because these data were not available in the NIS. However, even if we inflated our stroke rates on the assumption that 43% of the 30-day strokes occurred postdischarge [23], the overall stroke rate remains markedly low. Secondly, there is a high likelihood that coding specialists fail to capture many postoperative strokes in their hospital discharge abstracts [24]. While this limits extrapolation of data to nationwide estimates, the subgroup comparisons may still have relevance as the deficiencies are expected to affect both treatment groups in a balanced manner.

It should be noted that the cases included in this analysis represent a very small portion of the overall admissions with a primary diagnosis of ICAD and stroke (<0.1%). Utilization of intracranial stent placement and angioplasty remains stringent with patient selection typically reserved for clinical trials or as a last resort when medical therapy fails. Intervention in the setting of acute stroke is known to be extremely risky and warrants thorough consideration before being undertaken [25]. Within this select group, specific patient characteristics unable to be controlled for an administrative analysis may guide the endovascular approach and bias the treatment groups. A patient with a contraindication for dual antiplatelet therapy, and therefore stent placement, may reflect severe co-morbidities, thereby biasing the angioplasty-alone group toward worse outcomes. The stent placement group may have been biased by including bail-out cases in which angioplasty was not suitable due to a large dissection or significant recoiling of the lesion. Additionally, the vascular anatomy and lesion location are unknown, both of which likely impact the endovascular approach. While the anatomical variances cannot be accounted for, the use of the APR-DRG risk of mortality variable may mitigate some bias by controlling for comorbid diagnoses with particularly high risk of mortality. The angioplasty-alone group was observed to include a greater proportion of cases with an extreme risk of mortality. Multivariate analysis was performed to adjust for this variable and still found angioplasty alone to increase mortality.

The cost of stent placement was not associated with a significant increase in the total inpatient cost, compared to angioplasty-alone, in univariate and multivariate analysis. The device cost is most likely offset by a reduced length-of-stay in the stent placement group. The true cost to the healthcare system between approaches cannot be calculated in the present analysis and needs to account for long-term restenosis rates necessitating retreatment and any economic burden for subsequent strokes.

The limitations of the NIS are fairly broad and manuscripts have been written critiquing the validity of NIS studies [24,26]. The circumstances surrounding each patient's nonelective admission are unknown and the timing of symptom onset is not necessarily the day of admission. The proportion of cases admitted for nonfocal symptoms such as syncope, headache, or dizziness is unknown. We are also limited by uncertainty in the manner of diagnosis, likely ranging from clinical grounds to varying degrees of high Tesla magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT). This may affect how patients are coded and ultimately alter the study population and conclusions. No clinical information regarding stroke size, NIHSS, or degree of stenosis was available, which could present unknown bias in the group distribution. Additionally, due to the generality of certain ICD-9-CM codes, errors occur and researchers may incorrectly attribute a patient's preprocedural neurological status as a periprocedural complication, or vice versa. For this reason, we sought to focus this investigation on the "hard" endpoints of mortality and diagnosis codes specifically referencing postoperative origination. The accuracy of ICD-9-CM procedural codes related to endovascular angioplasty and stent placement have not been established. However, as the NIS is an administrative dataset based on billing information, we do not feel that stent placement would be frequently overlooked as it is a costly component of revascularization and reimbursement would be critical. The optimal timing of revascularization and the impact of hyperacute revascularization were beyond the scope of the present study and would need a larger cohort in order to stratify outcomes between temporal groups with adequate power. The limitations of the NIS also prevent us from ascertaining causal relationships and the anonymization prohibits patient follow-up. While these limitations are many and require investigation in prospective studies, they are common to any large administrative database examination, and the benefits of large database inspection include the ability to study medical practice at large without bias.

CONCLUSION

Patient outcome is multifactorial and administrative database analysis limits the ability to control for critical disease-specific variables. This study found the risk of mortality to be elevated following angioplasty alone. This may represent selection bias, as there was no difference in iatrogenic stroke rate between groups, but it also may indicate that patients with ICAD and acute stroke have increased odds of stenosis that is refractory to angioplasty alone and have a high risk of mortality with-

out revascularization. Our study would caution angioplasty alone as an arm of a future prospective randomized trial involving this severely burdened patient population requiring urgent intervention.

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